

Analysis of Reading Preferences of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Teachers' Educators

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Abstract

English is a global language and it plays its role as the second and official language in many countries. Untrained teachers, rote learning, grammar translation method and overcrowded classrooms are the factors which affect the process of language learning in the school sector. The study was designed to analyze reading preferences of literary and language habits of

Key Words

Reading Preferences,
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Teacher Educators of RITE colleges and faculty members. The sample of the study comprised 119 faculty members i.e. teachers' educators of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Responses were collected through a questionnaire. It was found that reading material has a positive relationship with the preferences of faculty members and teacher educators. It is suggested that faculty members may be provided with a variety of reading material and sources for their professional grooming of teaching.

Introduction

The English language learning process is highly challenging both for students and teachers in Pakistan. Rahman (2006) has pointed out that Pakistan is a poor country and the low literacy rate is the cause of poverty. English is the second and foreign language of the country which can provide the way to progress. As a result, people having a good command of the English language can earn a better living in Pakistan. English language, has occupied an inimitable position in the education system of Pakistan. In the National Educational Policy (2009) the government of Pakistan has considered English as compulsory subject. Science and Mathematics subjects are taught in English in all private and public sectors.

Aslam (2008) has divided the learning process into two categories: natural and systematic. In the natural process language is acquired and in the systematic process language is learned systematically. Native people acquire their native language, but the non-native people have to learn through proper consideration. The same is the case with Pakistani people as they also have to go through this painstaking process of language learning. There are many factors which contribute in making the language learning process ineffective in Pakistan.

Review of Related Literature

Rahman (2006) defined reading as a skill that makes the readers capable for identifying and understanding the written text. Reading is the activity which involves thought and awareness. Two processes involve such as word recognition and comprehension. Process of word recognition include one's spoked the written-text symbols of language whereas the ability to make logic about words and sentence is known as comprehension. Readers make use of different strategies to understand written text such as contextual knowledge, vocabulary, and grammatical knowledge.

Rahman (ibid.) pointed out that reading skills are predictable to have access to knowledge and information for individuals in the society. Language is rapidly changing due to latest and modern technologies. The process of reading depends on the language of the reader which he uses and the writing which he coded and encodes. Perfetti, Landi and Oakhill (2005) mentioned that the readers who have the problem of word identification are at risk because for comprehension.

DeKeyser (2007) stated that there were four techniques of reading such as skimming, scanning, extensive and intensive. He also defined skimming as reading to confirm prospects; it is

a tool for communication. Skimming is the most rudimentary type of reading as its objective is to familiarize the reader with the material as soon as possible to be read. Rahman (2006) stated that in skimming a reader go through the text quickly in order to get its central idea, understand its organization and comprehend the tone and intention of the writer. Aslam (2008) further stated that it is a technique that involves quick glancing through a text in order to understand its general content. The reader only frames an overall impression of the text that can be summed up in a word, phrase or sentence.

DeKeyser (2007) has indicated that scanning is used for getting general understanding by extracting specific information. It is a skill that requires how quickly you read with speed for exact information. Scan a reading text requires reading from top of the page. Then you have to rapidly move your eyes toward the bottom of the page. It is just a technique which is useful for looking the answer of a known question.

Nahrwold (2005) pointed out that intensive reading is normally a reading for accuracy. It involves approaching a text under the guidance of a teacher. It may be a task that influences a student to focus his attention on the text. It involves a deep and thorough understanding of a text. DeKeyser (2007) defined extensive reading as that type of reading which is used for fluency. It involves reading of longer texts but the purpose is to seek pleasure. It's not for minute details. The activity involves fluency which the students can read on their own. The entire school curriculum has a great amount of reading, through this technique the habit of reading outside the classroom can be developed among the students. Extensive reading can lessen the teachers' burden if he encourages his students to read without his help.

Pinnell (2008) stated that there are five basic elements of reading such as phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension. The phoneme is a smallest unit of speech sound in a word. In any specific language, each and every word is the combination of different sounds (Rauth & Stuart, 2008). In the English language there are 44 phonemes. Each produces its distinct sound in every word, e.g. /a, d, f, m/ in the words *apple, dog, fan, mango*, etc. Each word contains different sound e.g. *fan* is made up of three sounds i.e. /f,a,n/. Pinnell (2008) phonemic awareness is the knowledge of different sounds and its combination. John (2005) stated that if a person is not only able to identify the particular sound in a word but also can blend these sounds to form a word. So it can say that he has phonemic awareness.

Pinnell (2008) Phonics is the study of the relationship between a specific letter and its sounds. In every language there is a systematic relation between written letters and its spoken symbols. Rauth & Stuart (2008) stated that phonics is the method of teaching that aims to make students capable of identifying sounds of every letter and associate it with its symbol by using the knowledge of phonics. It leads to active reading and comprehension.

Pikulski and Chard (2005) defined Fluency exhibited in accurate, rapid, expression of oral reading. It is an ability to read a written text easily and effectively. Fluent readers have flow and smoothness. They are able to read the text effortlessly with exact pronunciation. Practice makes a man perfect. So fluency can be enhancing in the language learning process through reading the text again and again.

Diamond, Linda and Gutlohn (2006) stated that vocabulary is the knowledge of word and its meaning. Vocabulary is the stock of words which is used in every language. Language learning process can be make effective and successful, if learners become able to recognize words and its meaning. They also added that knowledge of vocabulary is the soul of language. Lack of the knowledge of vocabulary result in ineffective communication. The more words a reader know; the better communicator he will be.

Pressley et al. (2001) comprehension is the interaction of a reader with the text. It refers to relate what one is reading to what one already knows. Comprehension involves a very intense type of thinking that help a reader to make connection between prior knowledge and text. An active reader is capable to comprehend about the text by using different strategies like monitoring the text, making prediction and questioning.

Elliott (2010) stated that competency is the overall behaviour of the learner that includes questioning, calculating, solving problems, thinking critically which is needed for academic achievements. Wong (2007) mentioned that English language reading competency referred to the skill of a reader to read with exact pronunciations, expression, intonation and fluency. It is one of the major skill. Language competencies i.e. reading, writing, listening and speaking are required for academic purpose. Competency based language teaching involves which competency need to groom among the leaners and which competency a learner need to master. As Wong (2007) also stated that it is very essential to master a competency with the purpose of achieving a particular task. The objectives of the study was to identify the relationship of reading preferences with reading habits of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa teachers

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to find out the relationship of the reading preferences with reading habits of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa teacher educators.

Methodology

The design of the study was quantitative research. The study comprised 27 faculty members of Universities and 92 teacher educators of RITE from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa as sample of the research study. A questionnaire was developed which contains 35 items with two open ended questions. The eight (08) independent variables were identified which were correlated among respondents: Professional Groom, Professional Growth, Source of Reading, Mode of Reading, Time Hurdle, Language Preference, Purchasing and Literary Reading Preference. The data analysed as elaborated below:

Results

Table 1. Correlation of Purchasing Preferences and Professional Grooming

		Professional Grooming
Purchasing of books Preferences	Pearson correlation	0.200*
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.029
	Number	119

*. The significance level 0.05 of coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table 1 depicted that there is a strong relationship between purchasing and professional grooming as proved by Pearson $r(0.200)$ value with $p(0.029)$ and $p < 0.05$. The value of coefficient of correlation r is statistically significant which means that purchasing of reading material and professional grooming has positive correlation. The more teacher purchases the books for reading, the more they professionally groomed.

Table 2. Correlation of Professional Growth and Professional Grooming

		Professional Grooming
Professional Growth	Pearson correlation	.471**
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000
	Number	119

** The significance level 0.01 of coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table 2 reflected a strong relationship between professional growth and professional grooming as ascertained by Pearson $r(0.471)$ with $p(0.000)$ and $(p(0.000) < 0.05)$. The value of r is statistically significant which means that professional growth and professional grooming has the positive correlation between them.

Table 3. Correlation of Language and Literary Reading Preference

		Literary Preference
Language Preference	Pearson correlation	0.462**
	Next (2 tailed)	0.000
	Number	119

** The significance level 0.01 for coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table 3 represented a strong relationship between language preference and literary reading preference is existed as shown by Pearson $r(0.462)$ with $p(0.000)$ as $(p(0.000) < 0.01)$. The value of r is statistically significant which means that language preference and literary preference have a positive correlation.

Table 4. Correlation of Sources of Reading and Literary Reading Preference

		Literary Preference
Sources of Reading	Pearson correlation	0.399**
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000
	N	119

** The significance level 0.01 for coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table 4 depicted a strong relationship between source of reading and literary reading preference as verified by Pearson $r(0.399)$ with $p(0.000)$ and $(p(0.000) < 0.01)$ and hence, The value of r is statistically significant which means that source of reading and literacy reading preference has the positive correlation.

Table 5. Correlation of Source of Reading and Language Preference

		Language Preferences
Source of Reading	Pearson correlation	.312**
	p (2 tailed)	.001
	N	119

** . The significance level 0.01 for coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table. 5 showed that there is a strong relationship between source of reading and language preference as proved by Pearson $r(0.312)$ with $p(0.001)$ which is less than 0.05 ($p(0.001) < 0.01$) The value of r is statistically significant which means that sources of reading and language preference have positive correlation.

Table 6. Correlation of Purchasing and Literary Reading Preference.

		Literary Preference
Purchasing	Pearson correlation	0.327**
	p (2 tailed)	0.000
	N	119

** . The significance level 0.01 for coefficient of correlation (2 tailed).

Table 6 depicted that there is a strong relationship between purchasing and literary reading preference as demonstrated by Pearson $r(0.327)$ with $p(0.000)$ and ($p(0.000) < 0.01$). The value of r is statistically significant which means that purchasing and literary reading preference has the positive correlation.

Table 7. Correlation of Purchasing and Language Preferences.

		Language Preference
Purchasing	Pearson correlation	0.351**
	p (2 tailed)	0.000
	N	119

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 depicted that there is a strong relationship between purchasing and language preference as confirmed by Pearson $r(0.351)$ with $p(0.000)$ and ($p(0.000) < 0.01$). The value of r is statistically significant which means that purchasing and language preference has the positive correlation, the more teacher purchases the books for reading the more language preferences established.

Table 8. Correlation of Purchasing and Source of Reading.

		Source of Reading
Purchasing	Pearson correlation	.344**
	p (2 tailed)	0.000
	N	119

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 shown a strong relationship between purchasing and source of reading as proved by Pearson $r(0.344)$ value with p value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 ($p(0.000) < 0.01$). The value of r is statistically significant which means that purchasing and source of reading has the positive correlation, the more teacher purchases the books for reading the more sources for reading found.

Discussion and Conclusion

1. On the basis of table 1 and 2, it was found that there is a strong relationship among the respondents in terms of their reading preferences on professional growth and professional grooming. The more teacher purchases the books for reading, the more they professional groomed because they have vast sources of reading material. The result of the finding is consistent with Brooks (2007) teachers found themselves competent who read the books enhance which play its role in teaching and learning process experience. Furthermore, Cremin, Mottram, Beame and Goodwin (2008) study results found that teacher's personal preferences of reading develop students' reading habits which also make an impact on professional development and grooming of the teacher.
2. On the basis of table 3, 4 and 5, teachers have access to the reading sources which develop literary reading habits of both English and Urdu languages. The results of the findings are consistent with Hipple and Giblin

(1971) who elaborated that reading literature encouraged to develop reading habits which in result make positive influence on profession.

3. On the basis of table 6, 7, and 8, it was found that teacher purchases the source of literary reading materials such as books, magazines and other literary material they preferred in English and Urdu which reflects their teaching in the classroom. The results found consistent with Labercane (1986), Brooks (2007), Rudland and Kemp (2004) who found that preferences of reading material reflect the evidence of behaviour in the classroom. It meant that the more teacher reads, the more their behaviour makes an impact on students' performance. They also explained that professional reading provides substantial benefits to teachers for the development of understanding, improved teaching practices and positive outcomes, which is also identified in the study that the more teacher read the books the more professional growth developed.

Recommendations

It is suggested that faculty members may provide teachers with a variety of reading material and sources for their professional teaching. So that they formulate students learning with reference to their professional growth.

1. It is suggested that reading material such as prose, stories, novels, drama of English/Urdu language may be provided by the university administration in developing the literary taste of the students.
2. It is suggested that the sources of reading such as newspaper, magazine, articles, tablets, internet, social media (Facebook, WhatsApp) may be provided in the lecture hall for the English and Urdu content courses for developing language learning of the students.
3. It is suggested that easy access of literary material in libraries, resource centres and departmental libraries may be provided in the education department for English/Urdu language and literary growth of the teachers and students as well.
4. Purchasing the books is the main hurdle for readers to read. So it may be recommended that book sellers' services provide material in cheap prices which can be easy for readers to purchase.

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